

A Mathematical Model of Two-Layered Blood Flow with Volume Fraction of Micro-Organisms and Gravity Through a Narrow Diverging Vessel

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Abstract This paper is concerned with a mathematical analysis of the flow of blood with microorganisms in capillaries of small exponential divergence using two layered model. The model consists of a core region, enriched with various types of blood cells and a cell-free peripheral plasma layer. The expressions for axial velocity and flow rate have been obtained analytically. The effects of microorganisms and gravity have been discussed with the help of graphs. It is found that the velocity distribution increases for both gravity and volume fraction with an increase of divergence parameter, further as divergence parameter increases the velocity decreases for volume fraction.

Keywords: Two layered model, blood flow, dusty flow, divergence, gravity, pulsatile, volume fraction, Microorganisms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Blood flow through the cardio-vascular system is complex due to varying vessel geometrics, and the hemorheological characteristics of blood. Blood flow through capillaries is of great interest to physiologists involved in the research. Blood cannot be considered as a homogeneous fluid in these tubes and the two-phase nature of the blood causes several anomalous effects in its flow characteristics. According to [6] the most artifacts is the decrease in apparent viscosity with tube diameter and is known as Fahraeus-lindquist effect. There has been an increasing interest in the presence flow relationship, which characterized flow through tapered blood vessels. Most of this work has been directed towards the smaller vessels of the circulatory system, where the non-Newtonian effects are negligible. In narrow tubes cell depleted or cell free layers have been observed adjacent to tube wall. This is attributed by [23] to both mechanical exclusion of particles centre near the tube wall and radial migration of particles due to hydrodynamics force according [15]. The flow is found to be plugged near the tube axis and the extent of plug flow is seen to increase as the hematocrit is increased or the tube size is decreased. This phenomenon is analyzed by [9], [3], [7].

[16] studied the blood in two-layer model and came to the conclusion that the existence of the peripheral layer is helpful in functioning of the diseased arterial system. [14] have observed that the resistance coefficient increases rapidly with the ratio of core radius to tube radius and core eccentricity. [14] studied the transport of blood in a uniform and non-uniform tube and it is found that, for a given non-zero pressure drop, the flow rate increases as the viscosity of the peripheral layer decreases. [11] studied a theoretical model of blood flow in two-layer model for the distribution of red cells.

[2] considered the flow in tubes with small value of divergence parameter and [10] investigated the pressure distribution in a diverging tube. [1] extended [2] work

and [24] generalized the study for slender tubes by using a similarity technique which produces solutions for converging / diverging, compressible / incompressible flow with various wall profile shapes. [13] studied the pulsatile blood flow in a channel of small exponential divergence and the solutions revealed, that for low mean Reynolds numbers the viscous effects lead to radially dependent phase shifts between different layers of fluid oscillating in the axial direction and characteristic phase lags between flow and pressure curves.

[17] considered a two-layered model consisting of a core region of suspension of all the erythrocytes in plasma and a peripheral layer of plasma has been proposed to describe blood flow in small diameter vessels. [5] addressed the flow of blood in small diameter tubes using two layered model of micro polar and couple stress fluids, respectively. [20] & [21] studied the flow properties of peristaltic transport of blood in uniform tube have been investigated under various approximations. Blood is represented by two-layered fluid model consisting of a central layer of suspended particles with micro-organisms, assumed to be a couple-stress fluid, and a peripheral layer of plasma as a Newtonian fluid.

Aim of the present mathematical model is to study two layered blood flow with volume fraction of micro-organisms and gravity through a narrow diverging vessel by considering blood as homogeneous, isotropic, incompressible fluid with microorganisms, having a constant viscosity and density under the influence of pressure gradient. It is found that the velocity distribution increases for both gravity and volume fraction with an increase of divergence parameter, further as divergence parameter increases the velocity decreases for volume fraction. The analytical expressions for velocity and flow rates for both blood and microorganisms have been obtained. The changes in the velocity profiles are shown graphically.

II. FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

Let us consider a one-dimensional steady flow of blood through a rigid circular narrow tube with impermeable walls. The tube is considered to be diverging exponentially given by the relation

$$R(z) = \frac{R_0}{2} \left(1 + e^{\frac{\varepsilon z}{z_0}} \right)$$

Where ε the divergence parameter is over a characteristic axial distance z_0 and is considered to be very less than one and R_0 is the tube radius. Further, flow is assumed to be one-dimensional and axially symmetric.

The geometry of the flow is shown in Fig. 4.1. Based on [18], [12] model and with the above said assumptions the equation of motion of blood and microorganisms in two layer forms is given by

$$(1 - \phi)\rho \left\{ \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + (U \cdot \nabla_1)U \right\} = (1 - \phi) \left\{ -gradP + \mu \nabla_1^2 U - n \nabla_1^4 U \right\} + KN(V - U) + g \sin \psi$$

(1)

$$\left\{ \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + (V \cdot \nabla_1) V \right\} = \phi \left\{ -grad P + \mu \nabla_1^2 U - n \nabla_1^4 U \right\} + \frac{K}{m} (U - V) + g \sin \psi \tag{2}$$

$$\rho_2 \left\{ \frac{\partial W}{\partial t} + (W \cdot \nabla_1) W \right\} = \phi \left\{ -grad P + \mu_2 \nabla_1^2 W \right\} + g \sin \psi \tag{3}$$

The boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned} w_1, w_2 \text{ And } \nabla_1^2(w_1, w_2) & \text{ are all finite} && \text{at } r = 0 \\ w_1 = w_3 & \quad 0 < h < R && \text{at } r = h \\ w_1 = w_2 = w_3 = 0 \text{ And } \nabla_1^2(w_1, w_2, w_3) = 0 &&& \text{at } r = R \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Introduces the non-dimensional quantities

$$u = \frac{w_1 n \rho_1}{M}, \quad v = \frac{w_2 n \rho_1}{M}, \quad w = \frac{w_3 n \rho_2}{M}, \quad y = \frac{r}{R}, \quad g^* = \frac{g \rho R^2 n}{\mu M}, \quad \phi^* = \frac{\phi}{b}$$

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = M \cos(nt + \theta), \quad \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{R^2} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{1}{y} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right] = \frac{1}{R^2} \nabla^2 \tag{5}$$

The Fourier coefficient of the velocity analogous to the pressure gradient gives

$$\begin{aligned} u &= u_0(y) e^{int} \\ v &= v_0(y) e^{int} \\ w &= w_0(y) e^{int} \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

With the help of equations (5) and (6), the equations (1), (2) and (3) takes the form as,

$$(1 - \phi) \left\{ \nabla^4 u_0 - \bar{\alpha}^2 \nabla^2 u_0 - \bar{\alpha}^2 \alpha_1^2 e^{i\theta} + i \bar{\alpha}^2 \alpha_1^2 u_0 \right\} - \frac{\bar{\alpha}^2 b}{\beta} (v_0 - u_0) - \bar{\alpha}^2 g \sin \psi = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$v_0 = \frac{-\phi \beta}{\bar{\alpha}^2 b (1 + i \alpha_1^2 \beta)} \left\{ \nabla^4 u_0 - \bar{\alpha}^2 \nabla^2 u_0 - \bar{\alpha}^2 \alpha_1^2 e^{i\theta} \right\} + \frac{u_0}{1 + i \alpha_1^2 \beta} + \frac{\beta g \sin \psi}{b (1 + i \alpha_1^2 \beta)} \tag{8}$$

$$\nabla^2 w_0 - i \alpha_2^2 w_0 + \phi \alpha_2^2 e^{i\theta} + g \sin \psi \frac{1}{e^{int}} = 0 \tag{9}$$

The modified boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned} u_0, v_0 \text{ And } \nabla^2(u_0, v_0, w_0) & \text{ are all finite} && \text{at } y = 0 \\ u_0(h) = w_0(h), \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} = 0, & \quad 0 < h < y_1 && \text{at } y = h \\ u_0 = v_0 = w_0 = 0 \text{ And } \nabla^2(u_0, v_0, w_0) = 0 &&& \text{at } y = y_1 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

A. SOLUTION OF PROBLEM

Equation (7) is suited for finite Hankel transform technique of zeroth order. The transformation to be used is defined by [19].

$$\bar{u}_0(k) = \int_0^h u_0(y) y J_0(ky) dy \tag{11}$$

Where k is chosen as a positive root of the equation

$$kJ_0'(kh) + SJ_0(kh) = 0 \tag{12}$$

Where S is a constant (Stegun (2007))

The appropriate inversion formula is

$$u_0(y) = \frac{2}{h^2} \sum_k \frac{k^2 \bar{u}_0(k) J_0(ky)}{(S^2 + k^2) J_0^2(kh)} \tag{13}$$

Now applying the Hankel transform (11) and inverse transform (13) to equation (7) and using equation (6) and also the boundary conditions (10), we get the velocity of blood in non-dimensional form as,

$$u(y) = \frac{2e^{int}(L + \bar{\alpha}^2 \alpha_1^2 e^{i\theta})}{h} \sum_k \frac{k}{(S^2 + k^2)(C + iX)} \frac{J_1(kh)J_0(ky)}{J_0^2(kh)} \tag{14}$$

Where $C = k^4 + \bar{\alpha}^2 k^2 - \frac{4k^2}{h^4(S^2 + k^2)} + \frac{2k^3}{h(S^2 + k^2)} \frac{J_1(kh)}{J_0(kh)} - \frac{2k^3(k^2 + \bar{\alpha}^2)}{h(S^2 + k^2)} \frac{J_1(kh)}{J_0(kh)}$

$$X = \frac{\bar{\alpha}^2 \alpha_1^2 \{(1 - \phi b)(1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta) + b\}}{1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta(1 - \phi b)}, L = \frac{g \bar{\alpha}^2 \sin \psi (2 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta)}{1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta(1 - \phi b)} \tag{15}$$

With the help of equations (14) (15) and (6) equation (8) gives the velocity for microorganisms in non-dimensional form as,

$$v(y) = \frac{2}{h} \sum_k \frac{ke^{int}}{(S^2 + k^2)} \left\{ \frac{\beta g \sin \psi}{b(1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta)} - M^* L \right\} \frac{J_1(kh)J_0(ky)}{J_0^2(kh)} + u(y) \left\{ M^* X + \frac{1}{1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta} \right\} \tag{16}$$

Where $M^* = \frac{\phi \beta}{\bar{\alpha}^2 (1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta)}$

Homogeneous part of equation (14) is a modified Bessel equation and particular integral for the equation (14) is an imaginary quantity.

Hence the general solution of equation (14), the velocity plasma in non-dimensional form is

$$w(y) = u(h) \frac{(Ker_0(\alpha_2 y_1) Ber_0(\alpha_2 y) - Ber_0(\alpha_2 y_1) Ker_0(\alpha_2 y))}{(Ber_0(\alpha_2 h) Ker_0(\alpha_2 y_1) - Ber_0(\alpha_2 y_1) Ker_0(\alpha_2 h))} \tag{17}$$

Where $u(h) = \frac{2e^{int}(L + \bar{\alpha}^2 \alpha_1^2 e^{i\theta})}{h} \sum_k \frac{k}{(S^2 + k^2)(C + iX)} \frac{J_1(kh)}{J_0(kh)}$ (18)

B. FLOW RATE AND APPARENT VISCOSITY

The flow rate Q which is the volume of the suspension flowing per unit time across a cross-section of the tube, can be given by

Where $Q_s = 2\pi \int_0^h yu(y)dy + 2\pi \int_0^h yv(y)dy$ (19)

i.e.,

$$Q_s = 4\pi e^{int} \sum_k \frac{1}{(S^2 + k^2)} \frac{J_1^2(kh)}{J_0^2(kh)} \left\{ \left(L + \bar{\alpha}^2 \alpha_1^2 e^{i\theta} \right) \left[\frac{2 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta}{1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta} + M^* X \right] \sum_k \frac{1}{C + iX} + \frac{\beta g \sin \psi}{b(1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta)} - M^* L \right\} \tag{20}$$

$$Q_p = 2\pi \int_h^{y_1} yw(y)dy$$

$$Q_p = \frac{2\pi u(h)}{X_1} (X_2 - X_3) \tag{21}$$

Where $X_1 = ber_0(\alpha_2 h)ker_0(\alpha_2 y_1) - ber_0(\alpha_2 y_1)ker_0(\alpha_2 h)$

$$X_2 = \frac{1}{\alpha_2 \sqrt{2}} \{ y_1 ber_0(\alpha_2 y_1) [ker_1(\alpha_2 y_1) - kei_1(\alpha_2 y_1)] - hber_0(\alpha_2 y_1) [ker_1(\alpha_2 h) - kei_1(\alpha_2 h)] \}$$

$$X_3 = \frac{1}{\alpha_2 \sqrt{2}} \{ y_1 ker_0(\alpha_2 y_1) [ber_1(\alpha_2 y_1) - bei_1(\alpha_2 y_1)] - hker_0(\alpha_2 y_1) [ber_1(\alpha_2 h) - bei_1(\alpha_2 h)] \}$$

The Apparent viscosity, which shows a measure of the magnitude of flow resistance through a tube, is defined by the following relationship

The Apparent viscosity for blood (core region) is:

$$\mu_b = \frac{\mu_1 e^{i\theta}}{32} \sum_k \frac{(S^2 + k^2)(C + iX)}{(L + \alpha^{-2} \alpha_1^2 e^{i\theta})} \frac{J_0^2(kh)}{J_1^2(kh)} \tag{22}$$

Apparent viscosity for microorganisms:

$$\mu_m = \frac{\mu_1 e^{i\theta}}{32} \sum_k \frac{(S^2 + k^2)}{\frac{\beta g \sin \psi}{b(1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta)} - M^* L + \frac{(L + \alpha^{-2} \alpha_1^2 e^{i\theta})}{C + iX} [M^* X + \frac{1}{1 + i\alpha_1^2 \beta}]} \frac{J_0^2(kh)}{J_1^2(kh)} \tag{23}$$

Apparent viscosity for plasma:

$$\mu_p = \frac{\mu_1 e^{i\theta} X_1}{32u(h)(X_2 - X_3)} \tag{24}$$

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to illustrate the applicability of the present analytical study, the derived expressions have been computed for velocities of blood (both core and peripheral region) and microorganisms also for flow rates of blood and microorganisms. The distribution of velocities and flow rates are shown in figure 6. In fig 1 the variation of velocity profiles for blood and microorganisms are drawn for different values of pulsatile Reynolds number α_1^2 . Velocity profiles are directly proportional to pulsatile Reynolds number. From fig 2 it is observed that as gravity increases, the velocity for blood & microorganisms also increases. The velocity variation of blood and microorganisms for different values of nt and divergence parameter y_1 for fixed values of couple stress parameter and pulsatile Reynolds number is shown in fig 3. Fig 4 shows the velocity variation with volume fraction, it is observed that as volume fraction increases, velocity increases for both blood and microorganism. At the beginning the velocity increases slightly with increase in divergence parameter. Further as divergence parameter increases the velocity decreases slightly for plasma

layer. Comparing from fig 1 and 4, it is observed that there is appreciable change in velocity by increasing $\alpha_2^2 = 0.8$ to 2.0 in plasma layer. Microorganisms are concentrated only in the core region. The divergence of the tube does not effect the flow of microorganisms. At $nt = 15^0$, the core velocity is very high compared to microorganisms. As nt increases further the velocity of blood and microorganisms decreases upto 75^0 . The reverse flow for blood and microorganisms begins after 75^0 . It is observed from both the figures 1 and 3 that the velocity of plasma layer is very less compared to that of the core region.

Fig 5 shows the variation of plasma flow rate Q_p with nt and y_1 . As pulsatile Reynolds number α_2^2 increases from 0.8 to 2.0, then the flow rate decreases. The phase lag for plasma with pressure gradient is more compared to core region as shown in fig.6. The phase lag of plasma layer with pressure gradient curve increases slightly with a small increase in divergence parameter.

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fig 1. velocity variation with α_1^2 and y
 $(\alpha^2=0.68, \beta=0.2, \theta=\psi=nt=15^0, \phi=0.5, b=1, k=2.4, h=0.8, s=5, g=1)$
 —■— $\alpha_1^2=3$ - - - ■ - - - $\alpha_1^2=3$
 —★— $\alpha_1^2=4$ Blood - - - ★ - - - $\alpha_1^2=4$ Microorganisms
 —▲— $\alpha_1^2=5$ - - - ▲ - - - $\alpha_1^2=5$

fig 2. velocity variation with g and y
 $(\alpha^2=0.68, \alpha_1^2=4, \beta=0.2, \theta=\psi=nt=15^0, \phi=0.5, b=1, k=2.4, h=0.8, s=5)$
 —■— $g=1$ - - - ■ - - - $g=1$
 —★— $g=1.5$ Blood - - - ★ - - - $g=1.5$ Microorganisms
 —▲— $g=2.5$ - - - ▲ - - - $g=2.5$

fig 3. velocity variation with nt and y
 $(\alpha_1^2=4, \alpha^{-2}=0.68, \beta=0.2, \psi=\theta=15^\circ, h=0.8, \phi=0.5, g=1, k=2.4, s=5b=1)$
 $nt=15, 45, 75, 105$
 _____ blood - - - - - microorganisms

fig 4. velocity variation with $\phi=0.3, 0.5$ and y
 $(\alpha_1^2=4, \alpha^{-2}=0.68, \beta=0.2, nt=\psi=\theta=15^\circ, h=0.8, g=1, k=2.4, s=5b=1)$
 _____ blood - - - - - microorganisms

Fig.5. Variation of Plasma flow rate Q_p with nt and y_1

$$(\bar{\alpha}^2 = 4, \alpha_1^2 = 0.1, \beta = 0.2, b = 1, \phi = 0.5, \theta = \psi = 15^\circ, g = 1.0)$$

Fig.6. Variation of flow rate Q_s and Q_p with nt and y_1

$$(\bar{\alpha}^2 = 4, \alpha_1^2 = 0.1, \beta = 0.2, b = 1, \phi = 0.5, \theta = \psi = 15^\circ, g = 1.0)$$